

Path TSP Walks on Cubic Graphs

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Abstract

For every simple 2-vertex-connected cubic graph G on $n \geq 4$ vertices and every distinct pair of terminals $s, t \in V(G)$, there is a spanning s - t walk of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$, constructible in $O(n^2)$ time. If $st \in E(G)$, or if $st \notin E(G)$ and $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected, the bound improves to $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$; the improvement is constructive in the adjacent case and existential otherwise.

The proof converts the edge-rooted even-cover theorem of Wigal, Yoo, and Yu into a fixed-endpoint statement. The adjacent-terminal case opens an even cover at the terminal edge; for non-adjacent terminals, a constant-size split-and-subdivide gadget creates a marked edge whose contraction back to G forces a four-loop deletion, preserving the $5/4$ coefficient.

On simple cubic 3-edge-connected graphs the nonseparation condition is automatic, and combining the walk-length bound with $\text{LP}(G, s, t) \geq n - 1$ gives an asymptotic $5/4$ upper bound on the path Held–Karp gap. A complementary $9/8$ asymptotic lower bound follows from an exact adjacent-terminal LP certificate ($\text{LP} = n - 1$) and the Lukořka–Mazák cubic tour examples, so the asymptotic gap on this class lies in $[9/8, 5/4]$. The $5/4$ coefficient is tight on the broader simple 2-vertex-connected cubic class via the Dvořák–Kral’–Mohar tour examples.

1 Introduction

The graphic s - t path TSP asks for a shortest Hamiltonian path from s to t in the shortest-path metric of an unweighted graph G . Equivalently, it asks for a minimum-size connected spanning multigraph of G whose odd-degree set is exactly $\{s, t\}$. The standard lower bound is the path Held–Karp LP. For general graphic metrics, the integrality gap is asymptotically $3/2$ [12, 2], with later approximation ratios pushed below $3/2$ by tour-to-path reductions [14, 15]. In bounded-degree settings, Mömke–Svensson [8] give a $4/3$ tour Held–Karp bound on subcubic hosts, and Wigal–Yoo–Yu [16] sharpen this to a tight $5/4$ tour walk bound on simple 2-connected cubic graphs via an edge-conditioned even-cover/excess theorem.¹

This paper converts the WYY edge-rooted machinery into a *fixed-endpoint* statement for graphic s - t path TSP. Tour-to-path black-box reductions [15] give approximation-ratio reductions but no fixed-endpoint additive walk-length theorem of the present form; our result bounds $\text{OPT}(G, s, t)$ for every prescribed pair s, t and gives an exact LP certificate (Lemma 24); see Section 1.2 for the detailed comparison.

1.1 Results

Theorem 1 (Endpoint-conversion theorem). *Let G be a simple cubic 2-vertex-connected graph on $n \geq 4$ vertices, and let $s, t \in V(G)$ be distinct. Define the nonseparation indicator*

$$\varepsilon(G, s, t) := \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } st \in E(G), \text{ or } st \notin E(G) \text{ and } G - \{s, t\} \text{ connected,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

¹The cubic tour problem has a longer history: [6] gave the first sub- $3/2$ bound for cubic 3-edge-connected hosts; [1, 3, 4] subsequently improved or extended.

Then

$$\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - \varepsilon(G, s, t),$$

and a spanning s - t walk of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$ can be constructed in $O(n^2)$ time. The improvement $\varepsilon = 1$ is achieved constructively when $st \in E(G)$, since integrality of OPT and parity of n collapse the algorithmic bound $5n/4 - 3/2$ to $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$; when $st \notin E(G)$ and $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected, the $\varepsilon = 1$ improvement is currently existential.

The bound holds for every distinct pair of terminals, with no separation hypothesis: $\varepsilon = 0$ handles the separating non-adjacent regime, and the additive-one improvement $\varepsilon = 1$ covers the adjacent and the nonseparating non-adjacent regimes by two distinct mechanisms.

Remark 2 (Two mechanisms for the same $\varepsilon = 1$). The three terminal regimes reach the displayed bound by different arithmetic. At adjacent terminals one applies WYY directly to (G, st) with the base bound $\delta(G, st) \leq -1/2$ and no gadget loop loss; integrality of OPT and parity of n collapse $5n/4 - 3/2$ to $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$. At nonseparating non-adjacent terminals one applies WYY to the subdivided gadget (K, e^*) with the sharper bound $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -3/2$ (afforded by ruling out the rooted θ -chain exception via Lemma 14(d)) and the four-loop contraction loss; the two ingredients combine to yield the same $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$. At separating non-adjacent terminals only the base bound $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -1/2$ is available, and the four-loop loss is no longer enough to reach $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$; hence $\varepsilon = 0$ for that regime.

The coefficient $5/4$ cannot be improved for the full generality of the uniform bound: infinitely many simple 2-vertex-connected cubic hosts already saturate $5/4$ at adjacent terminals, via the Dvořák–Kráľ–Mohar examples for cubic graphic TSP.

Theorem 3 (Tightness of the $5/4$ coefficient on simple 2-vertex-connected cubic hosts). *There are infinitely many simple 2-vertex-connected cubic graphs G with an edge $st \in E(G)$ such that*

$$\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \geq 5|V(G)|/4 - O(1).$$

In particular, no bound of the form $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \alpha|V(G)| + O(1)$ with $\alpha < 5/4$ can hold for all instances satisfying the hypotheses of Theorem 1.

For the LP-gap application we restrict to simple cubic 3-edge-connected hosts (equivalently, simple cubic 3-vertex-connected; see Lemma 13). In that class the nonseparating-terminal condition is automatic, and the elementary Held–Karp lower bound $\text{LP}(G, s, t) \geq n - 1$ converts Theorem 1 into a sub- $3/2$ gap bound. We also prove that the same gap is bounded away from 1. Let

$$\Gamma_{\text{cub}} := \limsup_{\substack{n \rightarrow \infty \\ n \text{ even}}} \sup_{\substack{G, s, t: |V(G)|=n, \\ G \text{ simple cubic and 3-edge-connected}}} \frac{\text{OPT}(G, s, t)}{\text{LP}(G, s, t)},$$

where the supremum is over distinct terminals s, t . We prove the following two-sided statement.

Theorem 4 (Two-sided asymptotic gap window).

$$\frac{9}{8} \leq \Gamma_{\text{cub}} \leq \frac{5}{4}.$$

The two coefficients refer to distinct objects: the $5/4$ in Theorems 1 and 3 is an integer-optimum statement on the broader 2-vertex-connected cubic class, while the $9/8$ in Theorem 4 is a Held–Karp-gap lower bound on the narrower 3-edge-connected class via Lemma 24. The exact value of Γ_{cub} within $[9/8, 5/4]$ is open.

1.2 Techniques and comparison

Why endpoint conversion is non-trivial. The naive reduction — add a fictitious edge st and apply the WYY tour bound to $G + st$ — fails because adding st makes the endpoints have degree 4, violating the subcubic hypothesis of WYY. Two other natural attempts also fail. First, contracting any single edge incident to s (or t) to lower its degree creates a graph with a high-degree vertex elsewhere, again outside subcubic range. Second, treating $\{s, t\}$ as a fixed odd-degree set and running WYY’s tour algorithm on G does not produce an (s, t) -walk: WYY’s even-cover procedure is rooted at an *edge*, and its output joins the endpoints of that edge, not an arbitrary prescribed pair. Our endpoint conversion replaces these attempts with a constant-size split-and-subdivide gadget that creates a marked edge while preserving subcubicity, and recovers the budget through a four-loop contraction loss (Lemma 16).

Comparison with prior work. Three concrete points distinguish our setting from existing tour-to-path black-box reductions such as Traub–Vygen–Zenklusen [15]. First, our result is *fixed endpoint*: it bounds $\text{OPT}(G, s, t)$ for every prescribed pair s, t , rather than reducing to an approximation ratio for path TSP. Second, our $9/8$ lower bound rests on an exact adjacent-terminal LP certificate $\text{LP}(G, s, t) = n - 1$ (Lemma 24), a structural identity at the LP level, not a reduction. Third, our upper bound is a structural statement about cubic 2-vertex-connected hosts proved by constant-size gadget arguments rather than by an ε -loss reduction; in particular, no additive ε appears, and the constructive guarantee $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$ is exact up to one additive unit inherited from the WYY Scan estimate. Black-box reductions [15] produce neither Theorem 1 nor Lemma 24.

The $9/8$ lower bound is short but conceptually useful: combining the Lukočka–Mazák family of simple 3-connected cubic graphs with tour length $(9/8 - o(1))n$ [7] with the exact adjacent-terminal LP certificate (Lemma 24) transfers the cubic tour lower-bound examples directly to path LP-gap lower bounds.

What is new, and what we do not reprove. The edge-conditioned excess inequality, its exception theorem, and its quadratic-time even-cover procedure are due entirely to Wigal–Yoo–Yu [16]; we do not reprove any part of that machinery. Our contribution lies in a constant-size gadget that converts the WYY edge-rooted machinery into a fixed-endpoint statement on a non-adjacent terminal pair, the bookkeeping that keeps the $5/4$ coefficient through the contraction back to G , and the adjacent-terminal LP certificate $\text{LP} = n - 1$ that yields the $9/8$ path-LP-gap lower bound.

We use the Wigal–Yoo–Yu theorem [16] as a black box (see Section 3); below we record what existing tour-to-path frameworks do and do not give in our setting.

- TVZ [15] transfers an α -approximation for graphic TSP to an $(\alpha + \varepsilon)$ -approximation for graphic s - t path TSP. This is a black-box approximation-ratio reduction with additive ε loss; in particular, it gives neither a fixed-pair walk-length bound of the form $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - \varepsilon(G, s, t)$ (Theorem 1) nor an LP identity such as $\text{LP}(G, s, t) = n - 1$ (Lemma 24).
- Mömke–Svensson [8] bound the *tour* Held–Karp gap on subcubic graphs by $4/3$ via a matching-based framework. Their result lives on a different LP (tour, not path) and a broader graph class (subcubic, not cubic), and yields neither Theorem 1 nor Lemma 24.

Technical overview. WYY’s machinery controls an edge-rooted instance (H, e) through $\text{exc}(F) = 2c(F) + i(F)$ over even covers F containing e , and deleting e plus doubling a spanning tree in the component-contraction graph yields a u - v walk in $H - e$ of length $n(H) + \text{exc}(F) - 3$. The adjacent

case of Theorem 1 applies this directly to (G, st) ; the naive reduction for the non-adjacent case fails because adding a fictitious edge st makes the endpoints have degree 4, violating the subcubic hypothesis of Theorem 7. Our endpoint conversion replaces this with a constant-size split-and-subdivide gadget K in two ingredients, each addressing one obstruction. First, the *split* replaces s by adjacent vertices s_1, s_2 (and t by t_1, t_2) and adds the marked edge $e^* = s_2t_2$; this restores subcubicity by redistributing the three incidences of s over s_1, s_2 , but split alone is not enough, since contracting $\{s_1, s_2\}$ and $\{t_1, t_2\}$ back to s, t deletes only two internal edge-copies, costing one additive unit of budget. Second, the *subdivision* inserts degree-2 vertices p on s_1s_2 and q on t_1t_2 ; since p, q are non-terminal in any spanning (s_2, t_2) -join, they have positive even multidegree, so each contributes at least two edge-copies that become loops under the contraction $B_s = \{s_1, p, s_2\} \mapsto s$, $B_t = \{t_1, q, t_2\} \mapsto t$ (Lemma 16). The two ingredients are complementary: the split is for degree repair, and the subdivisions are for loop accounting; either alone leaves the $5/4$ budget short, but together they recover $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$ on G . The local exception checks in Lemma 14 (ruling out the connectivity, rooted θ -chain, and 2-edge-cut obstructions), simplicity, and $K \not\cong K_4$ (since K has degree-2 vertices) place the gadget outside the WYY exceptional layer, so $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -3/2$.

Organisation. Section 2 fixes notation and records the elementary path-LP lower bound $\text{LP} \geq n - 1$ used throughout. Section 3 proves the endpoint-conversion theorem, derives the $5/4$ upper bound and algorithmic corollaries, and proves coefficient-tightness on the broader simple 2-vertex-connected cubic class. Section 4 proves the adjacent-terminal LP certificate $\text{LP} = n - 1$ and the $9/8$ gap lower bound. Section 5 summarises the consequences and open problems.

2 Preliminaries

Throughout, “2-connected” means 2-vertex-connected; we write “2-edge-connected” or “3-edge-connected” explicitly when an edge-connectivity hypothesis is intended.

2.1 The path Held–Karp LP

Given a complete graph K_n with metric costs $c : \binom{V}{2} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ and endpoints $s, t \in V$, the *path Held–Karp LP* is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LP}(s, t) = \min \quad & \sum_e c_e x_e \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & x(\delta(v)) = 1 \text{ for } v \in \{s, t\}, \quad x(\delta(v)) = 2 \text{ for } v \in V \setminus \{s, t\}, \\ & x(\delta(S)) \geq 1 \text{ for } \emptyset \neq S \subsetneq V, |S \cap \{s, t\}| = 1, \\ & x(\delta(S)) \geq 2 \text{ for } \emptyset \neq S \subsetneq V, |S \cap \{s, t\}| \neq 1, \\ & 0 \leq x_e \leq 1 \text{ for every } e. \end{aligned}$$

For the graphic metric of $G = (V, E)$: $c_e = 1$ for $e \in E$ and $c_e = d_G(u, v) \geq 2$ for $\{u, v\} \notin E$. We write $\text{OPT}(G, s, t)$ for the path-TSP integer optimum on the same metric; equivalently, $\text{OPT}(G, s, t)$ is the minimum size of a spanning $\{s, t\}$ -join multigraph H of G , i.e., a connected spanning multigraph with odd-degree set exactly $\{s, t\}$.

Remark 5 (LP conventions). We adopt the boxed-edge form $0 \leq x_e \leq 1$. This matches the convention in much of the recent path-TSP literature (e.g., [12, 15]); some other works state the relaxation without the upper bound $x_e \leq 1$. All bounds in this paper are unaffected by that choice. For the lower bound, the certificate y constructed in Lemma 24 satisfies $y_e \in \{1/2, 1\}$, so it is feasible under either convention. For the upper bound, Lemma 6 only uses the singleton-degree equalities and $c_e \geq 1$. Throughout the paper, the integrality gap is OPT/LP with LP taken in the boxed form.

2.2 Elementary path-LP lower bound

Lemma 6. *Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph with $|V| = n$ and let $s, t \in V$. The path Held–Karp LP on the graphic metric of G satisfies $\text{LP}(G, s, t) \geq n - 1$.*

Proof. For any feasible x , summing the singleton degree constraints gives $2 \sum_e x_e = \sum_v x(\delta(v)) = 2(n - 2) + 2 = 2(n - 1)$, so $\sum_e x_e = n - 1$; since $c_e \geq 1$ for every edge of the graphic metric, $\text{LP} \geq n - 1$. \square

The converse $\text{LP} \leq n - 1$ fails in general, but for the adjacent-terminal instances needed in the lower-bound side below, equality $\text{LP}(G, s, t) = n - 1$ holds on every simple cubic 3-edge-connected host (Lemma 24).

3 The 5/4 upper bound and algorithmic form

We now prove the upper side of the gap window. The proof is a generalised $5n/4$ walk-length bound obtained via the edge-conditioned excess theorem of Wigal, Yoo, and Yu [16]. Combining the result with the elementary LP lower bound Lemma 6 gives the asymptotic 5/4 Held–Karp gap upper bound (with an explicit $O(1/n)$ correction at finite n ; see Corollary 18).

3.1 The Wigal–Yoo–Yu edge-conditioned excess theorem

Let G be a subcubic graph (simple in our applications, but the rooted WYY theorem below allows G to contain a parallel root edge or a loop while requiring $G - e$ to be simple). An *even cover* of G is a spanning subgraph $F \subseteq G$ with $d_F(v) \in \{0, 2\}$ for every $v \in V(G)$. Writing $c(F)$ for the number of cycles of F and $i(F)$ for the number of isolated vertices of F , set $\text{exc}(F) := 2c(F) + i(F)$. For $e \in E(G)$, let $\mathcal{E}(G, e)$ denote the family of even covers of G containing e , and define $\text{exc}_e(G) := \min_{F \in \mathcal{E}(G, e)} \text{exc}(F) - 2$. Write $n_2(G)$ for the number of degree-2 vertices of G .

Following [16], a *subcubic chain* from u to v is a simple connected subcubic graph obtained from 2-connected subcubic blocks (possibly single-vertex blocks) joined in series by cut-edges, with u and v the two endpoint vertices; in particular u and v each carry exactly one edge of the chain ([16, Fig. 1]). A *rooted θ -chain* is a pair (G, e) with $e = uv \in E(G)$ such that $G - e$ is the edge-disjoint union of two internally vertex-disjoint subcubic chains from u to v .

We use two separate consequences of Wigal–Yoo–Yu. The first is existential and concerns the optimum excess value $\delta(G, e)$; the second is algorithmic and uses the computable Scan estimate $\Delta(G, e)$. The additive-one difference between Theorem 11 and Corollary 21 comes precisely from replacing the sharper existential bound on δ by the available constructive bound on Δ .

symbol	meaning
$\text{exc}(F)$	cover excess of an even cover F : $2c(F) + i(F)$
$\text{exc}_e(G)$	rooted minimum excess: $\min\{\text{exc}(F) : F \in \mathcal{E}(G, e)\} - 2$
$\delta(G, e)$	rooted-excess deficit: $\text{exc}_e(G) - (n(G) + n_2(G))/4$
$\Delta(G, e)$	WYY Scan estimate, satisfying $\delta(G, e) \leq \Delta(G, e) \leq -1/2$

Table 1: Edge-rooted excess parameters used throughout Section 3. The two quantities $\text{exc}(F)$ and $\text{exc}_e(G)$ share a name but have different domains (a single cover versus a rooted graph). The deficit $\delta(G, e)$ is half-integer and is the quantity controlled by the Wigal–Yoo–Yu structural theorem; the Scan estimate $\Delta(G, e)$ is the computable surrogate used in the algorithmic form.

Theorem 7 (Wigal–Yoo–Yu rooted even-cover theorem, in the form used here; [16, Thm. 2.4]). *Let G be a 2-connected subcubic graph, and let $e = uv \in E(G)$ with $G - e$ simple. Define $\delta(G, e) := \text{exc}_e(G) - (n(G) + n_2(G))/4$. Then $\delta(G, e)$ is a half-integer, $\delta(G, e) \leq -1/2$, and if $\delta(G, e) \geq -1$ then at least one of the following holds: (i) G is a loop on a single vertex; (ii) $G \cong K_4$; (iii) e has a parallel edge in G ; (iv) e lies in a 2-edge-cut of G ; (v) (G, e) is a rooted θ -chain.*

We use [16, Thm. 2.4] only through the implication recorded in Theorem 7: if none of the configurations (i)–(v) holds, then half-integrality forces $\delta(G, e) \leq -3/2$. The original WYY statement provides finer structural information about the equality cases, which we do not use. In the black-box statement above we follow the degenerate conventions of [16], under which the single-vertex loop instance appears as a base exception; none of our applications falls into this case. The gadget lemmas below verify the remaining exceptions locally; no global characterization of WYY extremal graphs is needed. The translation from the WYY equality layer to the coarse list (i)–(v), together with the proof of Theorem 7 as a consequence of [16, Thm. 2.4], is deferred to Section A (Table 4).

The constructive form of WYY uses an algorithm `SCAN` that computes a half-integer value $\Delta(G, e) \geq \delta(G, e)$, and an even-cover algorithm `Algo(G, e, true)` that produces a cover whose excess is controlled by $\Delta(G, e)$. The branches of `SCAN` on 2-connected non- θ -chain inputs return $\Delta(G, e) \leq -1$. The detailed branch enumeration and its justification from [16] are recorded in Section A.

Lemma 8 (WYY constructive black box; [16, Algs. 1–2, Prop. 6.1, Prop. 6.2, and Cor. 6.8]). *Let (G, e) be as in Theorem 7. The WYY Scan phase computes, in $O(n(G))$ time [16, Prop. 6.2], a value $\Delta(G, e)$ satisfying*

$$\delta(G, e) \leq \Delta(G, e) \leq -1/2,$$

and the WYY algorithm `Algo(G, e, true)` outputs an even cover $F \in \mathcal{E}(G, e)$ with

$$\text{exc}(F) \leq (n(G) + n_2(G))/4 + \Delta(G, e) + 2$$

in total time $O(n(G)^2)$ [16, Cor. 6.8]. Moreover, in the 2-connected non- θ -chain branch the Scan estimate sharpens to

$$\text{If } G - e \text{ is 2-connected and } (G, e) \text{ is not a rooted } \theta\text{-chain, then } \Delta(G, e) \leq -1.$$

The justification of Lemma 8 from [16] (including the Scan branch enumeration that proves $\Delta \leq -1$ on 2-connected non- θ -chain inputs) and the notation dictionary mapping our quantities $\mathcal{E}(G, e), \text{exc}(F), \text{exc}_e(G), \delta(G, e), \Delta(G, e)$ to those of [16, §2–3, Alg. 1, Alg. 2] are deferred to Section A.

Remark 9. The constructive bound loses one additive unit relative to the existential bound, since Scan returns $\Delta \geq \delta$.

3.2 From an edge-rooted even cover to a spanning walk

Lemma 10. *Let G be a simple subcubic graph such that $G - e$ is connected, let $e = uv \in E(G)$, and let $F \in \mathcal{E}(G, e)$. Then $G - e$ admits a spanning (u, v) -walk of length at most $n(G) + \text{exc}(F) - 3$. Consequently, $\text{OPT}(G - e, u, v) \leq n(G) + \text{exc}_e(G) - 1$.*

Proof. F has $c := c(F)$ cycles and $i := i(F)$ isolated vertices, so $|E(F)| = n(G) - i$. Delete e : the cycle of F containing e opens into a u - v path; $F - e$ has $c + i$ components, $|E(F - e)| = n(G) - i - 1$, and odd-degree set $\{u, v\}$. Since $G - e$ is connected, the component-contraction multigraph of $(G - e)/(F - e)$ is connected, and the same is true after deleting its loops (an edge of $G - e$

becomes a loop in the component-contraction multigraph iff both its endpoints lie in the same component of $F - e$, so loop-deletion never disconnects components). The loopless part therefore admits a spanning tree T using $c + i - 1$ edges of $E(G - e) \setminus E(F)$. Doubling T and adjoining to $F - e$ yields a connected spanning multigraph W on $V(G)$ with odd-degree set $\{u, v\}$ (so W is a connected $\{u, v\}$ -join multigraph, equivalently a semi-Eulerian multigraph with endpoints u, v) and $|E(W)| = (n(G) - i - 1) + 2(c + i - 1) = n(G) + \text{exc}(F) - 3$. An Euler trail of W from u to v — equivalently, a semi-Eulerian u - v trail — has this length; minimising over $F \in \mathcal{E}(G, e)$ gives the bound. \square

3.3 The main bound

We now prove the existential bound of Theorem 1; the constructive companion ($O(n^2)$ algorithm reaching $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$) is recorded as Corollary 21 below. For convenience of the proof we name the existential statement separately and split it by terminal regime.

Theorem 11 (Existential part of Theorem 1). *Let G be a simple cubic 2-vertex-connected graph on $n \geq 4$ vertices, let $s, t \in V(G)$ be distinct, and let $\varepsilon(G, s, t) \in \{0, 1\}$ be the nonseparation indicator of Theorem 1. Then*

$$\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - \varepsilon(G, s, t).$$

Remark 12 (The case $n = 4$). The only simple cubic 2-vertex-connected graph on $n = 4$ vertices is K_4 , in which every pair s, t of distinct vertices is adjacent. Case A of the proof below applies via the WYY base bound $\delta(K_4, st) \leq -1/2$ (the value $\delta(K_4, st) = -1$ from exception (ii) of Theorem 7 is not needed); the argument yields $\text{OPT}(K_4, s, t) \leq 3 = \lfloor 5 \cdot 4/4 \rfloor - 2$, well within the stated bounds. Case B (the gadget) is vacuous at $n = 4$ since K_4 has no non-adjacent pair.

Lemma 13. *On simple cubic graphs, 3-edge-connectivity and 3-vertex-connectivity are equivalent. (Standard; proof in Section C.)*

By Lemma 13, every simple cubic 3-edge-connected graph is 3-vertex-connected. Hence $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected for every distinct non-adjacent pair s, t , and the hypotheses of Theorem 11 are automatic on the 3-edge-connected class.

The proof splits on whether st is an edge. When $st \in E(G)$ the base WYY inequality $\delta(G, st) \leq -1/2$ applies directly to (G, st) ; but when $st \notin E(G)$ the even-cover framework of [16] supplies no walk-length guarantee at the pair (s, t) , since $\{s, t\}$ is not the odd-degree set of any even cover. Our main technical ingredient is a constant-size reduction that converts the non-adjacent path instance into an edge-rooted instance: we construct an auxiliary *subdivided split gadget* (K, e^*) (Figure 1) from the split gadget J by subdividing its two internal edges, and show that (K, e^*) avoids all five exceptions of Theorem 7 so that $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -3/2$.

Why split and subdivide? The split gadget J is already simple cubic; its sole purpose is to create the marked edge $e^* = s_2t_2$. The subdivided gadget K inserts the degree-2 vertices p, q for a different reason: they force positive even multidegrees inside each contracted terminal block $B_s = \{s_1, p, s_2\}$ and $B_t = \{t_1, q, t_2\}$, so contraction $B_s \mapsto s, B_t \mapsto t$ deletes at least four internal edge-copies as loops (Lemma 16); this loop loss is what keeps the $5/4$ coefficient after returning to G .

The split gadget. Fix $s, t \in V(G)$ with $st \notin E(G)$, and write $N_G(s) = \{a, b, c\}$, $N_G(t) = \{d, g, h\}$; the six incidences sa, sb, sc, td, tg, th are distinct edges of G since G is cubic and $st \notin E$. Define the *split gadget* J from G (see Figure 1) as follows. First replace s by adjacent vertices s_1, s_2 , assigning

Figure 1: Endpoint-conversion gadget for the non-adjacent case $st \notin E(G)$: split (degree repair) followed by subdivision (loop accounting), then contraction back to G . Neighbour labels denote incidences and may coincide across the two sides in G .

the incidences sa, sb to s_1 and sc to s_2 . Replace t symmetrically by adjacent vertices t_1, t_2 , assigning td, tg to t_1 and th to t_2 . Finally add the marked edge $e^* := s_2t_2$. Thus, in the resulting graph J ,

$$N_J(s_1) = \{a, b, s_2\}, \quad N_J(s_2) = \{c, s_1, t_2\},$$

and symmetrically

$$N_J(t_1) = \{d, g, t_2\}, \quad N_J(t_2) = \{h, t_1, s_2\}.$$

Each of the six original incidences is redistributed to a unique new endpoint, and the three edges s_1s_2, t_1t_2, e^* are internal to the four fresh vertices. Hence no two edges of J share both endpoints. Explicitly, if a vertex z is adjacent to both s and t in G , then the two incidences become edges zs_i and zt_j for fresh vertices $s_i \neq t_j$, so they cannot form a parallel pair; no loop is introduced because $z \notin \{s, t\}$. Thus J is a simple cubic graph on $n + 2 \geq 8$ vertices with $n_2(J) = 0$, and $J - e^*$ is simple.

Example. On the triangular prism with s, t taken in opposite triangles, one has $|N_G(s) \cap N_G(t)| = 2$: each shared neighbour $z \in N(s) \cap N(t)$ contributes an edge to exactly one of $\{s_1, s_2\}$ and one of $\{t_1, t_2\}$ in J , and these two new edges land on distinct fresh vertices, so J remains simple.

We isolate the structural properties of the gadget into a single admissibility lemma. The four parts package what is needed to invoke Theorem 7 on (K, e^*) : parts (a)–(c) hold for every non-adjacent pair s, t , while part (d) (rooted θ -chain exclusion) is the place where the nonseparation hypothesis is used.

Lemma 14 (Gadget admissibility). *Let G be a simple cubic 2-vertex-connected graph on $n \geq 4$ vertices, and let $s, t \in V(G)$ be distinct with $st \notin E(G)$. Build J and the subdivided gadget K as above. Then:*

- (a) K is simple subcubic with $|V(K)| = n + 4$ and $n_2(K) = 2$ (the two subdivision vertices p, q);
- (b) $K - e^*$ is 2-vertex-connected;

- (c) (K, e^*) avoids exceptions (i)–(iv) of Theorem 7 (loop, K_4 , parallel root edge, root edge in a 2-edge-cut);
- (d) if additionally $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected, then (K, e^*) avoids exception (v) (rooted θ -chain).

Proof. Part (a) is immediate from the construction (verified case-by-case in Section B, including simplicity of J and K). For part (b), $J - e^*$ is 2-vertex-connected (Lemma 26) and subdivision preserves 2-vertex-connectivity (Lemma 27), so $K - e^*$ is 2-vertex-connected. Part (c): exceptions (i)–(iii) are excluded structurally (K is simple with $|V(K)| = n + 4 \geq 10$, so it is neither the one-vertex loop instance of (i) nor K_4 in (ii)); and the only $s_2 t_2$ -edge in K is e^* itself, so e^* has no parallel mate), and exception (iv) (root in a 2-edge-cut) follows from $K - e^*$ being 2-vertex-connected (hence bridgeless) via Lemma 29. Part (d) follows from the rooted θ -chain exclusion of Lemma 28, which uses the connectedness of $G - \{s, t\}$ exactly to ensure that $K - \{s_2, t_2\}$ is connected. \square

Lemma 15 (contraction preserves the walk). *Let M be a connected spanning (u, v) -join multigraph, and let $B_u, B_v \subseteq V(M)$ be disjoint vertex sets with $u \in B_u$, $v \in B_v$, such that every vertex of $(B_u \cup B_v) \setminus \{u, v\}$ has even M -degree. Contracting B_u to a single vertex s and B_v to a single vertex t , and dropping the resulting loops, yields a connected spanning $\{s, t\}$ -join multigraph M' on $(V(M) \setminus (B_u \cup B_v)) \cup \{s, t\}$ with $|E(M')|$ equal to $|E(M)|$ minus the number of internal edge-copies (edges with both endpoints in B_u or both in B_v) in M .*

Proof. Each edge of M internal to B_u or B_v becomes a loop after contraction and is dropped, so $|E(M')|$ equals $|E(M)|$ minus the number of such internal edge-copies. For the parity at s : every internal B_u -edge contributes 2 to $\sum_{w \in B_u} \deg_M(w)$, and the corresponding loop removes 2 from the merged degree; hence $\deg_{M'}(s) = \sum_{w \in B_u} \deg_M(w) - 2 \cdot (\# \text{internal edge-copies in } B_u)$, which has the same parity as $\sum_{w \in B_u} \deg_M(w) = \deg_M(u)$ (modulo 2, by the hypothesis on internal even degrees). Since $\deg_M(u)$ is odd, $\deg_{M'}(s)$ is odd; the same holds at t , and all other vertices retain even degree. Connectivity is preserved because quotienting a connected multigraph by any partition of its vertex set and dropping loops preserves connectivity. \square

Lemma 16 (Contraction loss: four loops in the subdivided gadget). *Let W be a connected spanning (s_2, t_2) -join multigraph of $K - e^*$ all of whose edges are copies of edges of $K - e^*$ (i.e., W is a multiset over $E(K) \setminus \{e^*\}$, with no self-loops; this is the structure produced by Lemma 10). After contracting $B_s = \{s_1, p, s_2\}$ to s and $B_t = \{t_1, q, t_2\}$ to t and deleting loops, the resulting connected spanning $\{s, t\}$ -join multigraph in G has at most $|W| - 4$ edges.*

Proof. Apply Lemma 15. Throughout this proof, all degrees are *multigraph degrees*: $\deg_W(v)$ is the number of edge-copies of W incident to v , with each parallel copy and each direction of a copy counted separately as it would be in any multigraph. Since K is a simple graph, no edge of $K - e^*$ is a self-loop, so a W -edge copying any underlying K -edge has its two ends at distinct vertices of K , and $\deg_W(v)$ exactly counts the number of edge-copies of W that touch v .

The vertices p and q are non-endpoints of W (the endpoints are s_2 and t_2), so their multigraph degrees in W are even; since W is connected and spanning $V(K)$, neither p nor q is isolated, hence $\deg_W(p), \deg_W(q) \geq 2$. By construction of K , every edge incident to p is one of $\{s_1 p, p s_2\}$, both with both endpoints in B_s , and every edge incident to q is one of $\{t_1 q, q t_2\}$, both with both endpoints in B_t . Thus the ≥ 2 edge-copies of W incident to p all lie inside B_s , and the ≥ 2 edge-copies incident to q all lie inside B_t . Hence W has at least four internal edge-copies (counted with multiplicity), all of which become loops under the contraction and are deleted. \square

Lemma 17 (Subdivided-gadget bookkeeping). *Assume $st \notin E(G)$ and $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected, and let (K, e^*) be obtained from the split gadget J by subdividing $s_1 s_2$ and $t_1 t_2$ at p and q . Then K is*

simple subcubic, $|V(K)| = n + 4$, $n_2(K) = 2$, $K - e^*$ is 2-connected, and (K, e^*) avoids all five exceptions in Theorem 7. Consequently the existential WYY bound gives a spanning s - t walk in G of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$. The constructive WYY bound used in Algorithm 1 gives one of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$.

For the parameters: J is simple cubic with $|V(J)| = n + 2$ and $n_2(J) = 0$; subdividing s_1s_2 at p and t_1t_2 at q yields K with $|V(K)| = n + 4$ and $n_2(K) = 2$, the two subdivision vertices p, q being the source of the loop loss in Lemma 16.

Proof. The graph parameters and 2-connectivity of $K - e^*$ are Lemma 14(a),(b); the five WYY exceptions are ruled out by Lemma 14(c),(d).

Existential bound. By Theorem 7, $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -3/2$, so $\text{exc}_{e^*}(K) \leq (n + 6)/4 - 3/2 = n/4$. Since $\text{exc}_{e^*}(K)$ is an integer, $\text{exc}_{e^*}(K) \leq \lfloor n/4 \rfloor$. Choosing a minimising $F \in \mathcal{E}(K, e^*)$ gives $\text{exc}(F) = \text{exc}_{e^*}(K) + 2 \leq \lfloor n/4 \rfloor + 2$. By Lemma 10 the walk in $K - e^*$ has length at most $(n + 4) + (\lfloor n/4 \rfloor + 2) - 3 = n + \lfloor n/4 \rfloor + 3 = \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor + 3$, using the identity $n + \lfloor n/4 \rfloor = \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$ valid for every integer $n \geq 0$. The four-loop loss of Lemma 16 subtracts 4, leaving a spanning s - t walk in G of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$.

Constructive bound. By Lemma 8, $\Delta(K, e^*) \leq -1$, so the WYY algorithm produces a cover with $\text{exc}(F) \leq (n + 6)/4 - 1 + 2 = (n + 10)/4$. By Lemma 10 the walk in $K - e^*$ has length at most $(n + 4) + (n + 10)/4 - 3 = (5n + 14)/4 = 5n/4 + 7/2$; the four-loop loss leaves a spanning s - t walk of length at most $5n/4 - 1/2$ in G , hence at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$ after integrality. \square

Both the existence proof of Theorem 11 below and Algorithm 1 use Lemma 17 in the subdivided gadget K . Table 2 (placed at the start of Section 3.5) summarises the resulting walk-length bounds across the three terminal regimes, side-by-side under the existential WYY input δ and the algorithmic Scan input Δ .

Proof of Theorem 11. Since G is cubic, n is even. We treat the three terminal regimes corresponding to the values of $\varepsilon(G, s, t)$ in turn.

Case A ($\varepsilon = 1$, adjacent): $st \in E(G)$. Since G is simple cubic and 2-vertex-connected, G is bridgeless; hence $G - st$ is connected and simple, satisfying the hypotheses of Theorem 7 for (G, st) . The base WYY inequality $\delta(G, st) \leq -1/2$ (Theorem 7) gives $\text{exc}_{st}(G) \leq n/4 - 1/2$, so by Lemma 10 $G - st$ admits a spanning (s, t) -walk of length at most $5n/4 - 3/2$, which is a walk of G . Integrality of OPT and n even yield $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$.

Case B ($\varepsilon = 1$, non-adjacent nonseparating): $st \notin E(G)$ and $G - \{s, t\}$ connected. Build the split gadget J and the subdivided gadget K as in Lemma 17. The existential WYY consequence gives the rooted-excess bounds displayed in that lemma, and its contraction bookkeeping converts the resulting (s_2, t_2) -walk in $K - e^*$ into a spanning s - t walk of G of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$. Hence $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$.

Case C ($\varepsilon = 0$, separating): $st \notin E(G)$ and $G - \{s, t\}$ disconnected. The theorem asserts only the uniform $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$ in this regime.

Build the same split gadget J and subdivided gadget K used in Case B. The construction itself does not use the connectedness of $G - \{s, t\}$: K is simple subcubic with $|V(K)| = n + 4$ and $n_2(K) = 2$, and Lemma 14(b) shows that $K - e^*$ is 2-vertex-connected (these proofs use only 2-vertex-connectivity and bridgelessness of G , never the connectedness of $G - \{s, t\}$). The remaining WYY exceptions are ruled out by structural reasons alone: K is simple (no loops or parallel edges to e^*), $|V(K)| \geq 10$ (so K is not K_4), and $K - e^*$ being 2-vertex-connected excludes the 2-edge-cut at e^* via Lemma 14(c). The only exception not necessarily ruled out is the rooted θ -chain (Lemma 14(d)

requires $G - \{s, t\}$ connected); but the *base* WYY bound $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -1/2$ (Theorem 7) holds without any exception avoidance and is all that is needed here.

From $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -1/2$ and $|V(K)| + n_2(K) = n + 6$,

$$\text{exc}_{e^*}(K) \leq \frac{n+6}{4} - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{n+4}{4}.$$

A minimising even cover $F \in \mathcal{E}(K, e^*)$ has $\text{exc}(F) = \text{exc}_{e^*}(K) + 2 \leq (n+4)/4 + 2 = n/4 + 3$. By Lemma 10, $K - e^*$ admits a spanning (s_2, t_2) -walk of length at most

$$|V(K)| + \text{exc}(F) - 3 \leq (n+4) + (n/4 + 3) - 3 = \frac{5n}{4} + 4.$$

Contracting B_s and B_t via Lemma 15 and applying the four-loop loss of Lemma 16 yields a spanning s - t walk of G of length at most $5n/4 + 4 - 4 = 5n/4$. Integrality of OPT gives $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. The existential statement is Theorem 11. The constructive statement is proved in Corollary 21 below. \square

3.4 Integrality gap and coefficient tightness

Corollary 18. *For every simple cubic 3-edge-connected graph G on $n \geq 4$ vertices and every distinct $s, t \in V(G)$,*

$$\frac{\text{OPT}(G, s, t)}{\text{LP}(G, s, t)} \leq \frac{\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1}{n-1} \leq \frac{5}{4} + \frac{1}{4(n-1)},$$

with the last inequality sharpened to $5/4 - 1/(4(n-1))$ when $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. In particular, for individual n with $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ the displayed bound is strictly below $5/4$, while for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ it can lie above $5/4$ by an additive $O(1/n)$ term; consequently the asymptotic Held–Karp gap on this class is at most $5/4$, but this estimate does not yield a finite- n bound uniformly below $5/4$.

Proof. By Lemma 13, every simple cubic 3-edge-connected graph is 3-vertex-connected, so $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected for every distinct pair s, t ; hence $\varepsilon(G, s, t) = 1$ on the entire class. Theorem 11 gives $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$, and combining with Lemma 6 gives the displayed inequality. \square

Corollary 19 (Path Held–Karp gap on the broader 2-vertex-connected class). *For every simple cubic 2-vertex-connected graph G on $n \geq 4$ vertices and every distinct $s, t \in V(G)$,*

$$\frac{\text{OPT}(G, s, t)}{\text{LP}(G, s, t)} \leq \frac{\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor}{n-1} = \frac{5}{4} + O(1/n).$$

In particular, the asymptotic path Held–Karp gap on this broader class is also at most $5/4$; the additive-one improvement of Corollary 18 on the 3-edge-connected subclass uses the automatic nonseparation provided by Lemma 13.

Proof. Theorem 11 with $\varepsilon = 0$ gives $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$ for every distinct pair, with no separation hypothesis; Lemma 6 gives the matching denominator $\text{LP}(G, s, t) \geq n - 1$. \square

Corollary 20 (Two-sided asymptotic gap bounds). $9/8 \leq \Gamma_{\text{cub}} \leq 5/4$, *where Γ_{cub} is the even-order limsup supremum from the introduction. The lower bound is Theorem 25; the upper bound is Corollary 18. This proves Theorem 4.*

3.5 Algorithmic form

terminal regime	Existential (Theorem 7)		Algorithmic (Lemma 8)	
	WYY input	walk in G	WYY input	walk in G
$st \in E(G)$	$\delta \leq -1/2$	$\leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$	$\Delta \leq -1/2$	$\leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$
$st \notin E(G), G - \{s, t\}$ conn.	$\delta \leq -3/2$	$\leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$	$\Delta \leq -1$	$\leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$
$st \notin E(G)$, separating	$\delta \leq -1/2$	$\leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$	$\Delta \leq -1/2$	$\leq \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$

Table 2: Walk-length bounds across the three terminal regimes, under the existential WYY deficit δ (Theorem 7) and the algorithmic Scan estimate Δ (Lemma 8). The rooted graph is G in the adjacent regime and the subdivided gadget K otherwise (Figure 1); details and the intermediate $|V| + n_2$ and pre-floor walk lengths are in Lemma 17. The single-unit gap between the existential and algorithmic columns occurs only in the non-adjacent nonseparating regime; this is the source of the additive-one discrepancy noted after Theorem 1.

Corollary 21 (Algorithmic form). *Algorithm 1 runs in $O(n^2)$ time and, given a simple cubic 2-vertex-connected graph G on $n \geq 4$ vertices and any distinct terminals $s, t \in V(G)$, outputs a spanning s - t walk of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$. When $st \in E(G)$, the same algorithm in fact outputs a walk of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$ (adjacent column of Table 2).*

Algorithm 1 Path TSP walk on simple cubic 2-vertex-connected graphs

Require: simple cubic 2-vertex-connected G on $n \geq 4$ vertices; distinct $s, t \in V(G)$ (no separation hypothesis)

Ensure: spanning s - t walk of G of length at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$

- 1: **if** $st \in E(G)$ **then** ▷ Case A
 - 2: $(H, e) \leftarrow (G, st); (u, v) \leftarrow (s, t)$
 - 3: **else** ▷ Case B
 - 4: build split gadget J with marked edge $e^* = s_2t_2$; subdivide s_1s_2 at p and t_1t_2 at q to get K
 - 5: $(H, e) \leftarrow (K, e^*); (u, v) \leftarrow (s_2, t_2)$
 - 6: $F \leftarrow \text{Algo}(H, e, \text{true})$ ▷ WYY even-cover algorithm of Lemma 8
 - 7: $F' \leftarrow F - e$; let M be the multigraph on the connected components of $(V(H), F')$ whose edges are the images in $H - e$ of the non- F edges under component contraction (the *component-contraction multigraph*; cf. Lemma 10)
 - 8: $T_M \leftarrow$ spanning tree of the loopless part of M ; choose one preimage edge in $E(H - e) \setminus E(F)$ for each edge of T_M to form T_H ; $W \leftarrow F' \cup 2T_H$ ▷ double T_H so each F' -component is reached and left; Lemma 10
 - 9: **if** Case B **then**
 - 10: $W_G \leftarrow W$ with $\{s_1, p, s_2\} \mapsto s, \{t_1, q, t_2\} \mapsto t$, loops deleted ▷ Lemmas 15 and 16
 - 11: **return** Euler trail from s to t of W_G via Hierholzer
 - 12: **else**
 - 13: **return** Euler trail from s to t of W via Hierholzer
-

Proof. Case A applies the base WYY bound $\Delta(G, st) \leq -1/2$ directly to (G, st) , giving $\text{exc}(F) \leq n/4 + 3/2$ and, by Lemma 10, a walk of length at most $5n/4 - 3/2$. Since G is cubic, n is even, so $5n/4 \in \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{Z}$; the walk length is integral, hence at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$ (when $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, $5n/4 - 3/2 = \lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 1$ already; when $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, $5n/4 - 3/2$ is a half-integer and rounds down to $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - 2$).

Case B builds the subdivided gadget K as in Lemma 17. Whether or not $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected, K is simple subcubic, $|V(K)| = n + 4$, $n_2(K) = 2$, $K - e^*$ is 2-vertex-connected (Lemma 14(b), neither using $G - \{s, t\}$ connected), and $K - e^*$ is bridgeless, ruling out the 2-edge-cut WYY

exception (Lemma 14(c)). The WYY Scan estimate therefore returns $\Delta(K, e^*) \leq -1/2$ in all cases (the base bound of Lemma 8); when in addition $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected, Lemma 14(d) rules out the rooted θ -chain exception and Scan sharpens to $\Delta(K, e^*) \leq -1$. Either way, the WYY algorithm applied to (K, e^*) outputs an even cover with $\text{exc}(F) \leq (n + 6)/4 + \Delta(K, e^*) + 2 \leq n/4 + 3$, hence by Lemma 10 a spanning (s_2, t_2) -walk of $K - e^*$ of length at most $5n/4 + 4$. Contracting B_s and B_t via Lemma 15 and applying the four-loop loss of Lemma 16 yields a spanning s - t walk of G of length at most $5n/4$. Since walk length is integral, it is at most $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$.

All steps other than the WYY even-cover procedure are linear-time graph operations; the WYY procedure dominates at $O(n^2)$. \square

Implementation notes for Algorithm 1 (input/output conventions of the WYY black box, the component-contraction multigraph, and the multigraph semantics of $W = F' \cup 2T_H$) are recorded in Section D.

3.6 Tightness of the 5/4 coefficient on simple 2-vertex-connected cubic hosts

The next theorem records that the 5/4 coefficient in Theorems 1 and 11 is best possible for the full simple 2-vertex-connected cubic domain. This is an integer optimum statement for the broader endpoint-conversion theorem; it should not be confused with the Held–Karp gap lower bound on the more restrictive 3-edge-connected class, which is Theorem 25.

Theorem 22 (Tightness of the 5/4 coefficient on simple 2-vertex-connected cubic hosts). *There are infinitely many simple 2-vertex-connected cubic graphs G on n vertices and edges $st \in E(G)$ such that*

$$\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \geq 5n/4 - 3.$$

Consequently, no estimate of the form $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \alpha n + O(1)$ with $\alpha < 5/4$ can hold over all instances satisfying the hypotheses of Theorem 11.

Proof. Dvořák, Král', and Mohar [5] exhibit a family of simple 2-connected cubic graphs whose shortest graph-TSP tour has length $5n/4 - O(1)$; Wigal, Yoo, and Yu use the same family in their sharpness discussion and record the precise bound $\text{tsp}(G) \geq 5n/4 - 2$ ([16, Sec. 7]; the original construction is [5]). Let G be one of these graphs. The choice of st is arbitrary: for every edge $st \in E(G)$, adding one copy of st to any spanning s - t walk closes it into a tour, so $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \geq \text{tsp}(G) - 1 = 5n/4 - 3$. Since these are adjacent-terminal instances, they satisfy the hypotheses of Theorem 11. The final claim follows by taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ along the family. \square

Proof of Theorem 3. This is Theorem 22. \square

Remark 23. Theorem 22 shows that no coefficient below 5/4 is possible for the full simple 2-vertex-connected endpoint-conversion statement. For the narrower 3-edge-connected LP-gap problem, the structural exclusions used above drive $\delta(K, e^*) \leq -3/2$ for the subdivided gadget; improving the WYY-based route would require excluding this $\delta = -3/2$ layer on a positive-density scale, not merely obtaining further constant-size savings.

4 A 9/8 Held–Karp gap lower bound

The upper bound from Section 3 is complemented by a lower bound on the same LP gap. The key observation is that, when the two terminals are adjacent, the trivial lower bound $\text{LP} \geq n - 1$ is tight on every simple cubic 3-edge-connected host. In the proof below, bridgelessness is used

only to obtain a perfect matching through the terminal edge; the Held–Karp cut feasibility uses 3-edge-connectivity.

Lemma 24 (Adjacent-terminal LP certificate). *Let G be a simple cubic 3-edge-connected graph on n vertices, and let $st \in E(G)$. Then the path Held–Karp value for terminals s, t satisfies*

$$\text{LP}(G, s, t) = n - 1.$$

Proof. The lower bound $\text{LP}(G, s, t) \geq n - 1$ is Lemma 6. For the reverse inequality, choose a perfect matching M of G containing the edge st ; such an M exists by the Schönberger–Plesník 1-factor theorem [9, 11, 10] (every edge of a bridgeless cubic graph lies in a perfect matching). Define $y \in \mathbb{R}^{E(G)}$ by

$$y_e = \begin{cases} 1, & e \in M, \\ 1/2, & e \in E(G) \setminus M. \end{cases}$$

Every vertex has y -degree $1 + 2 \cdot (1/2) = 2$. Let $\emptyset \neq S \subsetneq V(G)$. Since G is 3-edge-connected, $|\delta(S)| \geq 3$. If $|\delta(S)| \geq 4$, then $y(\delta(S)) \geq |\delta(S)|/2 \geq 2$. If $|\delta(S)| = 3$, then $|S|$ is odd because G is cubic, and a perfect matching crosses an odd cut an odd number of times; hence $k := |M \cap \delta(S)| \in \{1, 3\}$, and $y(\delta(S)) = k + \frac{1}{2}(3 - k) = \frac{3+k}{2} \geq 2$.

Thus y is feasible for the tour Held–Karp relaxation and $y_{st} = 1$. Set $x := y - \chi^{st}$ (extended by zero outside $E(G)$). Then x has degree 1 at s, t , degree 2 elsewhere, satisfies the s - t path cut constraints, and obeys $0 \leq x_e \leq 1$. Its cost is $|M| + \frac{1}{2}|E(G) \setminus M| - 1 = n/2 + n/2 - 1 = n - 1$, so $\text{LP}(G, s, t) \leq n - 1$. \square

Why adjacent terminals? For non-adjacent terminals on the 3-edge-connected cubic class the LP value may be strictly larger than $n - 1$, so choosing *adjacent* terminals minimises the denominator of the gap ratio: Lemma 24 shrinks $\text{LP}(G, s, t)$ to $n - 1$, the smallest value compatible with Lemma 6. Combined with any cubic tour lower-bound example, this immediately transfers the tour-side $(1 - o(1))$ ratio improvement to the path version.

Theorem 25 (A $9/8$ lower bound for the path Held–Karp gap on simple cubic 3-edge-connected hosts). *The asymptotic Held–Karp integrality gap for graphic s - t path TSP on simple cubic 3-edge-connected graphs is at least $9/8$. Equivalently, $\Gamma_{\text{cub}} \geq 9/8$.*

Proof. Lukořka and Mazák construct a sequence of simple 3-connected cubic graphs G_k , with $n_k := |V(G_k)| \rightarrow \infty$, whose graphic tour-TSP optimum satisfies

$$\text{tsp}(G_k) \geq (9/8 - o(1))n_k$$

[7]. Since 3-connected graphs are 3-edge-connected, these hosts lie in our class. Fix any edge $s_k t_k \in E(G_k)$. Any feasible s_k - t_k path-TSP multigraph becomes a feasible tour-TSP multigraph after adding one copy of $s_k t_k$. Hence

$$\text{OPT}(G_k, s_k, t_k) + 1 \geq \text{tsp}(G_k),$$

and therefore

$$\text{OPT}(G_k, s_k, t_k) \geq (9/8 - o(1))n_k - 1.$$

By Lemma 24, $\text{LP}(G_k, s_k, t_k) = n_k - 1$. Thus

$$\frac{\text{OPT}(G_k, s_k, t_k)}{\text{LP}(G_k, s_k, t_k)} \geq \frac{(9/8 - o(1))n_k - 1}{n_k - 1} = \frac{9}{8} - o(1).$$

Taking the limsup over this sequence gives the claim. \square

5 Consequences and open problems

Theorems 11 and 22 give a coefficient-tight endpoint-conversion theorem on the full simple 2-vertex-connected cubic domain: the upper bound is $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor - \varepsilon(G, s, t)$ for every distinct terminal pair, and the coefficient $5/4$ cannot be lowered without imposing additional structure. The Held–Karp conclusion is deliberately narrower. On simple cubic 3-edge-connected hosts, Corollary 20 gives

$$\frac{9}{8} \leq \Gamma_{\text{cub}} \leq \frac{5}{4}.$$

The lower endpoint $9/8$ comes from adjacent terminals on 3-connected cubic tour lower-bound examples and the exact adjacent-terminal LP certificate; the upper endpoint $5/4$ is supplied by the WYY-to-path endpoint conversion. Since Theorem 22 rules out a coefficient below $5/4$ for the broader 2-vertex-connected domain, any improvement for the 3-edge-connected LP gap must exploit genuinely 3-edge-connected or LP-specific structure. Within the Wigal–Yoo–Yu route, this means new information about the next excess layer (Remark 23).

A natural open question is whether the same gadget argument extends to simple 2-vertex-connected *subcubic* hosts with $\deg_G(s) = \deg_G(t) = 3$ and $G - \{s, t\}$ connected, with the analogous bound $\text{OPT}(G, s, t) \leq \lfloor (5n + n_2(G))/4 \rfloor$; a full proof would require re-verifying Lemma 10–Lemma 17 under the weaker subcubic hypothesis with the $n_2(G)$ bookkeeping handled in tandem. The remaining subcubic challenges are to handle endpoints of degree 2 and hosts that are merely 2-edge-connected; both require new decomposition ideas. Beyond the cubic setting, stronger vertex-connectivity assumptions may force substantially better endpoint behavior; for example, Thomassen [13] proved that every 4-connected planar graph is Hamiltonian-connected.

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A WYY translation: notation, exception layers, and Scan

This appendix records, in one place, exactly which statements of Wigal–Yoo–Yu [16] the main proofs invoke and how each piece is translated into the notation of Section 3. The material is not new, but the dependence is non-trivial: the existential bound Theorem 7 uses both the deficit inequality and the equality-layer characterisation of [16, Thm. 2.4], and the algorithmic bound Lemma 8 uses three specific branch values of the Scan procedure of [16, Alg. 1]. We list these citations explicitly in Table 3 and translate them in Tables 1 and 4 and in the proofs below.

WYY citation	where used in this paper
[16, Thm. 2.4(T1)] (deficit inequality)	baseline $\delta(G, e) \leq -1/2$ in Theorem 7
[16, Thm. 2.4(T1)] (equality layer at $\delta = -1/2$)	exceptions (i), (v) at $\delta = -1/2$ in Theorem 7
[16, Thm. 2.4(T3)] ($\delta = -1$ characterisation)	exceptions (ii)–(v) at $\delta = -1$ in Theorem 7
[16, Alg. 1] (SCAN)	defines $\Delta(G, e)$ in Lemma 8
[16, §6, definition of G_u] (u -suppression)	smaller instance (G_u, f_u) in branch (c2)
[16, Alg. 1 & Prop. 6.1] (Scan branch values)	values $\Delta \in \{-3/2, -1, -1/2\}$ in branches (c1)–(c3)
[16, Prop. 6.2] (Scan running time)	$O(n)$ Scan time, contributes to $O(n^2)$ total
[16, Alg. 2] (Algo(G, e, true))	even cover with bound on $\text{exc}(F)$
[16, Cor. 6.8] (consolidated guarantee)	combined output and timing in Lemma 8

Table 3: Exact citations from [16] used in this paper. The entries are ordered by where they enter the argument.

A.1 Mapping the WYY equality layer to our coarse exceptions

WYY layer	WYY extremal type	our coarse exception (i)–(v)
$\delta = -1/2$	loop instance	(i) G is a loop
$\delta = -1/2$	balanced tight rooted θ -chain	(v) rooted θ -chain
$\delta = -1$	(K_4, e)	(ii) $G \cong K_4$
$\delta = -1$	suppression image of a parallel root edge	(iii) e has a parallel edge
$\delta = -1$	suppression image of a 2-edge-cut at e	(iv) e lies in a 2-edge-cut
$\delta = -1$	near-minimal rooted θ -chain	(v) rooted θ -chain

Table 4: Mapping from the WYY equality and near-equality cases [16, Thm. 2.4(T1)/(T3)] to the coarse exception list (i)–(v) of Theorem 7. Distinct WYY extremal types may collapse onto the same coarse exception.

Proof of Theorem 7 from [16, Thm. 2.4]. The inequality $\delta(G, e) \leq -1/2$ is [16, Thm. 2.4(T1)], and the half-integrality of $\delta(G, e)$ follows from the parity observation preceding that theorem. Suppose $\delta(G, e) \geq -1$; by half-integrality, $\delta(G, e) \in \{-1, -1/2\}$, so it suffices to show that each of these equality cases falls inside the listed configurations.

If $\delta(G, e) = -1/2$, then [16, Thm. 2.4(T1)] characterises (G, e) : G is a loop on a single vertex (configuration (i)) or (G, e) is a tight rooted θ -chain extremal (configuration (v)).

If $\delta(G, e) = -1$, then [16, Thm. 2.4(T3)] provides the structural description: $(G, e) \cong (K_4, e)$ (configuration (ii)), e has a parallel edge in G (configuration (iii)), e lies in a 2-edge-cut of G (configuration (iv)), or (G, e) is a rooted θ -chain instance at the $\delta = -1$ layer (configuration (v)).

Hence in either equality case, at least one of (i)–(v) holds. Excluding all five configurations therefore forces $\delta(G, e) \leq -3/2$. \square

A.2 The WYY Scan procedure and its branches

For the algorithmic form, we recall three named pieces of [16].

The *Scan estimate* $\Delta(G, e)$ is the half-integer value returned by the procedure $\text{SCAN}(G, e)$ of [16, Alg. 1]. By design, SCAN is an explicit *verifiable upper estimate* on the rooted-excess deficit: $\Delta(G, e) \geq \delta(G, e)$ for every (G, e) in the WYY hypothesis [16, Prop. 6.1]. When the analysis branches on $\Delta(G, e)$ rather than the (possibly smaller) optimum $\delta(G, e)$, the algorithmic guarantee loses one additive unit relative to the existential one.

The *canonical u -suppression* is the local move defined in [16, §6, before Algorithm 1]. Given (G, e) with $e = uv$ and $G - e$ a 2-connected subcubic graph, u has degree 2 in $G - e$; suppressing u in $G - e$ deletes u and replaces its two $G - e$ -incidences by a single edge f_u joining u 's two $G - e$ -neighbours. The result is the smaller rooted instance (G_u, f_u) used by SCAN at line 6 of [16, Alg. 1].

The *rooted θ -chain branch* of SCAN is the case (C1) below, where the input itself is a rooted θ -chain; the *suppressed- θ -chain branch* is the case (C2), where instead the u -suppression is a rooted θ -chain. In all other configurations SCAN falls into the *generic branch* (C3).

Justification of Lemma 8 from Wigal–Yoo–Yu. We quote the displayed estimates, the even-cover construction, and the running time as direct consequences of [16, Algs. 1–2, Prop. 6.1, Prop. 6.2, and Cor. 6.8]. In our notation: $\Delta(G, e)$ is the value returned by the Scan procedure of [16, Alg. 1], which is the explicit upper estimate on $\delta(G, e)$ established in [16, Prop. 6.1] (so $\Delta(G, e) \geq \delta(G, e)$), and

$\Delta(G, e) \leq -1/2$ matches the half-integer baseline of Theorem 7 (= [16, Thm. 2.4]). The relation $\text{exc}(F) \leq (n(G) + n_2(G))/4 + \Delta(G, e) + 2$ is the output guarantee of the even-cover algorithm $\text{Algo}(G, e, \text{true})$ of [16, Alg. 2], whose overall correctness and $O(n^2)$ running time are consolidated in [16, Cor. 6.8] (the Scan procedure itself runs in linear time [16, Prop. 6.2]); the additive $+2$ corresponds to the rooted-edge shift recorded in Table 1.

We isolate the special branch used here. When $G - e$ is 2-connected, the Scan procedure does not recurse through cut-vertices (i.e., it does not enter lines 1–3 of [16, Alg. 1]), and its output $\Delta(G, e) \in \{-3/2, -1, -1/2\}$ is determined branch-by-branch by [16, Alg. 1, lines 4–9] according to whether the rooted instance, or its canonical u -suppression, is a rooted θ -chain. The specific values in each branch are read off from [16, Prop. 6.1]:

- (C1) If (G, e) is itself a rooted θ -chain (the half-integer extremal configuration of Theorem 7(v)), Scan returns $\Delta(G, e) = -1/2$ at [16, Alg. 1, line 5]; the bound $\delta(G, e) \leq -1/2$ is [16, Lem. 3.1].
- (C2) Otherwise Scan applies the canonical u -suppression in $G - e$ to produce a smaller rooted instance (G_u, f_u) . If (G_u, f_u) is a rooted θ -chain, Scan returns $\Delta(G, e) = -3/2$ at [16, Alg. 1, line 7]; the bound $\delta(G, e) \leq -3/2$ is [16, Lem. 3.3].
- (C3) If neither (G, e) nor (G_u, f_u) is a rooted θ -chain, Scan returns $\Delta(G, e) = -1$ at [16, Alg. 1, line 9]; the bound $\delta(G, e) \leq -1$ is [16, Thm. 2.4].

The structural statements underlying [16, Prop. 6.1] are Lemmas 3.1 and 3.3 and Theorem 2.4 of [16] (our Theorem 7); we use only the values displayed above. In particular, when $G - e$ is 2-connected and (G, e) is not a rooted θ -chain, case (C1) is excluded, so $\Delta(G, e) \in \{-3/2, -1\}$, hence $\Delta(G, e) \leq -1$ as displayed. \square

A.3 Notation dictionary

For comparison with [16], the correspondence between our notation and theirs is as follows. The family $\mathcal{E}(G, e)$ of even covers containing the rooted edge, the cover excess $\text{exc}(F) = 2c(F) + i(F)$, and the rooted minimum $\text{exc}_e(G) = \min_{F \in \mathcal{E}(G, e)} \text{exc}(F) - 2$ are exactly the quantities used in [16, §2–3] (with the same shift -2 absorbing the rooted-edge contribution). The deficit $\delta(G, e) := \text{exc}_e(G) - (n(G) + n_2(G))/4$ is the half-integer controlled by [16, Thm. 2.4], and the Scan estimate $\Delta(G, e)$ is the value computed by the Scan procedure of [16, Alg. 1]; the even-cover output of Lemma 8 is $\text{Algo}(G, e, \text{true})$ from [16, Alg. 2].

B Sub-lemmas of gadget admissibility

The four sub-lemmas below decompose the proof of Lemma 14. We restate them with appendix labels.

Lemma 26 (2-connectivity of the split gadget). *If G is 2-vertex-connected then $J - e^*$ is 2-connected; in particular so is J .*

Proof. Write $H := J - e^*$. We show $H - x$ is connected for every $x \in V(H)$.

Case $x \notin \{s_1, s_2, t_1, t_2\}$. The contraction $s_1s_2 \mapsto s, t_1t_2 \mapsto t$ sends H onto G (the edge e^* is already removed, and s_1s_2, t_1t_2 become loops that are dropped), hence $H - x$ onto $G - x$. Both contracted edges s_1s_2, t_1t_2 survive in $H - x$, and contracting an edge both of whose endpoints already lie in the same component of $H - x$ neither merges nor splits components: the equivalence classes of the quotient relation “ $u \sim v$ iff u, v lie in the same component of $H - x$ ” are exactly the preimages of

the components of $G - x$, since the only effect of the contraction is to identify $\{s_1, s_2\}$ and $\{t_1, t_2\}$, each pair already internal to a single component. Thus the components of $H - x$ and of $G - x$ are in canonical bijection. Since G is 2-vertex-connected, $G - x$ is connected, and therefore so is $H - x$.

In each of the four endpoint cases below, G is simple cubic and 2-vertex-connected; in particular, every edge of G lies on a cycle, so G has no bridge and edges such as sc or th are non-bridges.

Case $x = s_1$. In $H - s_1$ contract the edge t_1t_2 to a single vertex, which may be identified with the original vertex t of G (its three G -incidences td, tg, th are recovered from t_1d, t_1g, t_2h). The resulting graph is $(G - s) + s_2$ with s_2 joined to $c \in V(G) \setminus \{s, t\}$ by the single edge s_2c . By 2-vertex-connectivity of G , $G - s$ is connected; attaching the pendant vertex s_2 via s_2c preserves connectedness. Contraction does not change the number of connected components, so $H - s_1$ is connected.

Case $x = s_2$. This is structurally different from $x = s_1$: in J the incidences at s_2 are $\{s_1s_2, s_2c, e^*\}$, and since e^* is already absent in $H = J - e^*$, deleting s_2 from H removes exactly the edges s_1s_2 and s_2c . Now contract t_1t_2 to the vertex t of G , as in the previous case. The resulting graph is isomorphic to $G - sc$, where s_1 plays the role of s (its remaining H -incidences s_1a, s_1b recover sa, sb). Bridgelessness of G implies that sc is not a bridge, so $G - sc$ is connected; hence so is $H - s_2$.

The cases $x = t_1$ and $x = t_2$ are now obtained by interchanging the roles of s and t (and of the neighbours $\{a, b, c\} \leftrightarrow \{d, g, h\}$): repeat the argument with s_1s_2 contracted instead of t_1t_2 , yielding $(G - t) + t_2$ with pendant t_2h in case $x = t_1$, and $G - th$ in case $x = t_2$ (again connected because th is not a bridge of the bridgeless graph G). \square

Lemma 27 (Subdivision preserves 2-connectivity). *If H is 2-vertex-connected and H' is obtained from H by subdividing one edge, then H' is 2-vertex-connected.*

Proof. Let the subdivided edge be xy , and let r be the new vertex. For an old vertex $z \in V(H)$, the graph $H' - z$ is obtained from the connected graph $H - z$ either by replacing the surviving edge xy with the path xry , or, if $z \in \{x, y\}$, by attaching the new vertex r as a leaf to the other endpoint. Hence $H' - z$ is connected. Finally, $H' - r = H - xy$ is connected because no edge of a 2-vertex-connected graph is a bridge. Thus deleting any vertex of H' leaves a connected graph. \square

Lemma 28 (Non- θ structure of the split gadgets). *Assume $G - \{s, t\}$ is connected, and let K be obtained from J by subdividing s_1s_2 and t_1t_2 at p and q , respectively. Then both $J - \{s_2, t_2\}$ and $K - \{s_2, t_2\}$ are connected. Consequently, neither (J, e^*) nor (K, e^*) is a rooted θ -chain.*

Proof. The graph $J - \{s_2, t_2\}$ is obtained from $G - \{s, t\}$ (connected by hypothesis) by attaching s_1 via s_1a, s_1b and t_1 via t_1d, t_1g ; the edges s_1s_2, t_1t_2 , and e^* are incident to the removed vertices. Since $\{a, b, d, g\} \subseteq V(G) \setminus \{s, t\}$, this graph is connected. The graph $K - \{s_2, t_2\}$ is obtained from $J - \{s_2, t_2\}$ by attaching the new pendant vertices p to s_1 and q to t_1 (in K , the edges s_1p and t_1q remain after deleting s_2, t_2 , which removes ps_2 and qt_2). Hence it is also connected.

If (J, e^*) were a rooted θ -chain, then $J - e^*$ would be the edge-disjoint union of two internally vertex-disjoint subcubic s_2 - t_2 chains; in particular, by definition of the chain decomposition, no edge of $J - e^*$ joins an internal vertex of one chain to an internal vertex of the other.

We rule out the *trivial-chain case* directly. A subcubic chain from s_2 to t_2 with no internal vertex is, by definition, a single edge from s_2 to t_2 . Such a single-edge chain in $J - e^*$ would be a second s_2t_2 -edge in J ; but by construction, the only s_2t_2 -edge in J is e^* itself, and no other edge of J has both endpoints in $\{s_2, t_2\}$. So neither chain of the putative θ -decomposition can be trivial. Each chain therefore contains at least one internal vertex, and deleting s_2, t_2 from J separates the internal vertex sets of the two chains. This contradicts the connectedness of $J - \{s_2, t_2\}$. The same argument applies to K : by construction, K also has no s_2t_2 -edge other than e^* (the subdivision vertices p, q

lie on the side edges s_1s_2, t_1t_2 , not on e^*), so the rooted- θ chains of $K - e^*$ would still each need an internal vertex, contradicting the connectedness of $K - \{s_2, t_2\}$. \square

Lemma 29 (Root edge cannot lie in a 2-edge-cut). *Let H be a connected graph and let $e \in E(H)$. If $H - e$ is connected and bridgeless, then e does not lie in any 2-edge-cut of H . In particular, if $H - e$ is 2-vertex-connected, then the WYY exception that e lies in a 2-edge-cut is impossible.*

Proof. If $\{e, f\}$ were a 2-edge-cut of H , then $H - \{e, f\}$ would be disconnected. Since $H - e$ is connected, deleting f from $H - e$ then disconnects it, so f is a bridge of $H - e$, contradicting the hypothesis. A 2-vertex-connected graph is connected and has no bridge, giving the last assertion. \square

C Cubic 3-edge-connectivity equals 3-vertex-connectivity

Proof of Lemma 13. First, G has no cut vertex. If v were a cut vertex, then the components of $G - v$ would receive altogether the three edges incident to v . Some component would therefore be joined to the rest of the graph by at most one edge, contradicting 3-edge-connectivity.

Now suppose that $\{u, v\}$ is a 2-vertex cut. If $uv \in E(G)$, then the components of $G - \{u, v\}$ receive altogether four edges from $\{u, v\}$, so one component is joined to the rest of the graph by at most two edges, again a contradiction.

Thus $uv \notin E(G)$. The six edges incident to u or v are distributed among the components of $G - \{u, v\}$. To avoid an edge cut of size at most two, there must be exactly two components, say A and B , and each must receive exactly three of these six edges. Let a be the number of edges from u to A . Then v has $3 - a$ edges to A , while u and v have $3 - a$ and a edges to B , respectively. Since neither u nor v is a cut vertex, $a \in \{1, 2\}$. If $a = 1$, then $A \cup \{v\}$ is separated from the rest of G by exactly two edges; if $a = 2$, then $A \cup \{u\}$ is separated by exactly two edges. Both cases contradict 3-edge-connectivity. Hence no 2-vertex cut exists. The reverse direction is the standard inequality $\kappa(G) \leq \lambda(G) \leq \delta(G) = 3$: if G is simple cubic and 3-vertex-connected, then $\lambda(G) \geq \kappa(G) = 3$ and $\lambda(G) \leq 3$, so G is 3-edge-connected. \square

D Implementation notes for Algorithm 1

The existential theorem uses the exact minimum excess from Theorem 7, whereas Algorithm 1 uses only the Scan estimate Δ from Lemma 8. In the non-adjacent case, the base Scan bound $\Delta(K, e^*) \leq -1/2$ suffices for the uniform constructive $\lfloor 5n/4 \rfloor$ guarantee; under the additional nonseparation hypothesis $G - \{s, t\}$ connected, Lemma 14(d) excludes the rooted θ -chain branch and sharpens the Scan estimate to $\Delta(K, e^*) \leq -1$. The degree-2 vertices p, q absorb the remaining budget because their traversals become loops under the $K \rightarrow G$ contraction.

A few input/output conventions are used implicitly in lines 3–7 of Algorithm 1. The black-box call $\text{Algo}(H, e, \text{true})$ expects H simple subcubic with $H - e$ simple, returns a subgraph $F \subseteq H$ rather than a multiset, and is guaranteed by Lemma 8 to satisfy $F \in \mathcal{E}(H, e)$ and $\text{exc}(F) \leq (n(H) + n_2(H))/4 + \Delta(H, e) + 2$. The component-contraction multigraph M has one vertex for every connected component of $(V(H), F')$, including isolated vertices of F' as their own singleton components, and one parallel edge for each $H - e$ -edge whose two endpoints lie in distinct F' -components; loops of M correspond to $H - e$ -edges with both endpoints in the same F' -component and are not used. The spanning tree T_M is taken in the loopless part of M , after which the preimage step lifts each edge of T_M to one specific $H - e$ -edge to form T_H . At this point F' is still a subgraph of H but $W = F' \cup 2T_H$ is a multigraph: each edge of T_H contributes two parallel copies to W ,

while edges of F' contribute one. The Hierholzer step then operates on W as a multigraph in the usual sense.